

The Agave Fibers in Composite Materials

Ridha BEN CHEIKH, Sami BEN BRAHIM, Mohamed BAKLOUTI, Béchir HADJ SASSI

Ecole Nationale d'Ingenieurs de Tunis, BP 37, Le Belvédère, Tunis (TUNISIA)

SUMMARY : A new method to extract the agave fibers from the leaves is described. It consists of hydrolysing the leaf in 3N NaOH aqueous solution during 48 hours followed by a dioxane washing.

The extracted fibers have medium performances compared to glass fibers (tensile modulus : 11.52GPa, tensile strength : 475.1MPa, deformation : 18.2%).

We worked different composite test tubes using unsaturated polyester and polyepoxyde matrix reinforced by 1 to 5 Agave fibers. We compared their mechanical behaviour under one direction strength to composite test tubes reinforced by glass fibers and we have noticed that for the same fibers filling up, the performances of composites reinforced by agave fibers is near equal to those reinforced by glass fibers. We have also noticed that the agave fibers adhere to polyester and polyepoxyde matrix better than the glass fibers.

KEYWORDS : Agave fibers, Sisal fibers, Polyester agave composite, Polyépoxyde agave composite

INTRODUCTION

Few years ago, scientists have shown that some synthetics fibers, used in composite materials, are harmful to the human environment [1,2]. This fact has pushed researchers to find other forms of fibers which are both useful and safe.

For some applications, natural fibers are good candidates to substitute for man made fibers because they are safe, since they become from the nature. Besides, they present many interesting characteristics spread over several domains.

In this context, we have chosen to study some mechanical characteristics of Agave fibers and their behaviours in polymeric matrix and these for two essential reasons : the first is to know if it is possible to use these fibers in some composite applications as a substitute to synthetic fibers, the second one is to try to find a use for the big quantities of agave plants, present in the Tunisian territory, in an interesting industrial applications.

The agave is a plant which belongs to the amaryllidacies family. It is widely cultivated in Tunisia, especially near the coasts.

The agave plant (Fig.1) is composed of big and sharped leaves from which fibers, called agave or sisal fibers, are extracted.

Fig.1 The Agave plant

Anatomy of the agave leaves [3]

The agave leaves are constituted of a mesophyll limited by two epidermis and crossed by nervures which have different sizes (Fig.2). Every nervure is constituted of a vascular bundles (phloem and xylem) supported by nerve fibers and surrounded by a cellulosic sheath (Fig.3,4).

1-upper epidermis, 2-lower epidermis, 3-mesophyll, 4-nervures

Fig.2 Agave leaf section

The leaves are preserved in alcohol 70°. The sections are coloured with Acetic carmine iodine. The pink tissues are cellulosic, The green tissues are lignified.

In the young whitish Agave leaves, the fibers are still alive and present thin cellulosic walls (Fig.3).

Fig.3 Detail of a nervure

1-cellulosic sheath, 2-xylem, 3-phloem, 4-periphloem fibers, 5-perixylem fibers.

In the adult leaves, the fiber walls become thicker and tend to be lignified. The lignin is a strong and watertight body that crosses the cellulosic fiber walls and makes them stiffer. Lignified fibers are dead fibers (Fig.4).

Fig.4, Nervure showing a bundles of completely lignified fibers

The quantity of lignin injected in the cellulosic fiber walls is about 11% of their total composition. This makes them sufficiently supple. This quantity is more important in the case of wood fibers ; for this reason they are very stiff. On the other hand, cotton fibers are completely cellulosic.

This anatomy study allows us to affirm that the long fibers that we extract mechanically or chemically are composed of bundles of lignified microfibers placed on end. To make their mechanical and statistical manipulation easier, we will consider one agave fiber, as the bundles of fibers extracted from a nervure.

Extraction of agave fibers

There are two processes to extract fibers : the mechanical process and the chemical process.

The mechanical process consists of scrapping the leaves with machines called « raspadors » under a jet of water [4]. This process is firstly expensive because it needs a lot of water and energy. Secondly, it can modify, by scrapping, some mechanical characteristics of fibers.

The chemical process, largely used in the past, consists of attacking leaves by sea water (hydrolysis in sea water) in order to dissolve the pulp and to extract the fibers. This process requires nearly 3 months.

We have developed a chemical process that is able to extract fibers in 48 hours and which consists of attacking fibers by a 3N sodium hydroxide solution. The obtained fibers are washed in water and then in a dioxane solution. This solution eliminates all the residue of pulp surrounding the fiber surface and makes it clean and white. The same results are obtained by the use of an aqueous solution of NaClO.

Physical and mechanical characteristics of agave fibers :

We have compared the physical performances of fibers extracted by the three methods presented above and we have noticed (table 1) that the smallest diameter correspond to the fibers extracted by sodium hydroxide and washed for 24 hours in dioxane, followed by the diameter of the scrapped fibers, then by the diameter of fibers extracted by sodium hydroxide and washed half an hours in dioxane and finally by the diameter of fibers extracted by sea water. Obviously, the fibers density progresses in the opposite direction of their diameter.

Table 1 : Physical characteristics of agave fibers

Extraction mode	Fiber diameter (mm)	Fiber density
Hydrolysis in NaOH 3N, washed 24h in dioxane	0,106	1,99
Hydrolysis in NaOH 3N, washed 1/2h in dioxane	0,139	1,41
Hydrolysis in sea water	0,148	1,32
scrapping	0,135	1,45

We have also compared, according to the instructions of the standard : ISO 3341, the mechanical performances of these different types of fibers, and we have noticed (table 2) that the highest tensile modulus corresponds to the fibers extracted by sodium hydroxide and washed for 24 hours in dioxane, followed by the tensile modulus of fibers extracted by sodium hydroxide and washed for half an hour in dioxane, followed by the tensile modulus of fibers extracted by sea water and finally by scrapped fibers.

Table 2 : Mechanical characteristics of agave fibers

Extraction mode	Tensile modulus (GPa)	Deformation (%)	Tensile strength (MPa)
Hydrolysis in NaOH 3N, washed 24h in dioxane	11.52	18.2	475.1
Hydrolysis in NaOH 3N, washed 1/2h in dioxane	6.13	20.7	299.6
Hydrolysis in sea water	4.63	35.9	407.4
scrapping	4.03	34.2	352.6

We have also noticed that the deformation of fibers progresses in the opposite direction of their tensile modulus with 34.5% for fibers extracted by sea water and 18.5% for the fibers extracted by sodium hydroxide and washed for 24 hours in dioxane. Finally, we have noticed that the highest tensile strength corresponds to the fibers extracted by sodium hydroxide and washed for 24 hours in dioxane :455MPa.

Figure 5 presents the model behaviour of the fibers in a classical tensile mechanical test and shows that the fibers which are not washed in dioxane have the highest deformation. These information allow us to say that the dioxane solution dissolves the residue of the pulp fixed to the surface of the fibers. This pulp is very elastic, thus it increases the fibers deformation.

Fig. 5 : Model conventional curves of fibers in a mechanical tensile test

The composite material reinforced by agave fibers :

With the extracted fibers, we have worked up different composites : the first is constituted of polyester matrix and reinforced by agave fibers, the second is composed of polyester matrix and reinforced by glass fibers and finally, the third is composed of polyepoxyde matrix and reinforced by agave fibers.

Table 3 gives the technical characteristics of the resins and the fibers used to work up the above mentioned composites

Table 3 : Technical characteristics of the resins and the fibers used

	Viscosity 23°C (mPa.s)	Density	Tensile modulus (MPa)	Strength modulus (MPa)	Deformation (%)
Polyester resin	180	1.1	3600	5.5	2
Polyepoxyde resin	240	1.6		80	3.5
Agave fibers		1.33	5550	297	21.5
Glass fibers		2.60	73000	3400	4.5

We have produced about 200 test-tubes by molds that we made according to the ISO 527-5 instructions. (Fig. 6)

Fig. 6 : Test-tubes mold

We have performed mechanical tensile tests according to the same standard and we noticed that for the polyester matrix reinforced by agave fibers, the tensile modulus and the tensile

strength increase with the number of fibers. In the other hand, the fibers deformation decreases.(table 4)

Table 4 : Mechanical characteristics of the worked up composites

Composite type	Number of fibers	Tensile modulus (MPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Deformation (%)
Polyester reinforced by agave fibers	0 fiber	1622.99	40.78	5.91
	1 fiber	1716.82	42.74	4.36
	2 fibers	1786.73	44.10	4.23
	3 fibers	1858.99	46.70	4.06
	4 fibers	1926.19	47.58	3.42
	5 fibers	2014.59	50.21	3.53
Polyester reinforced by glass fibers	5 bundles of fibers	2215.15	51.25	3.02
Polyepoxyde reinforced by agave fibers	0 fiber	1884.34	48.31	3.38
	5 fibers	2097.44	48.43	2.97

We have also noticed that for the same fibers filling up coefficient, the performances of polyester matrix reinforced by glass fibers are nearly the same as those of polyester matrix reinforced by agave fibers, even though the glass fibers are ten times more resistant than the agave fibers. Finally, the performances of polyepoxyde matrix reinforced by agave fibers is very close to those of the other composites presented above.

Figure 7 presents the conventional model curves of the different composites presented in table 4 and shows the increase of the tensile modulus and the strength modulus with the number of fibers.

Fig.7: the mode curves of the different types of composites in a tensile test

In summary, we notice that the agave fibers increase the resistance of the composite, and that these fibers adhere to polyester and polyepoxyde matrix better than the glass fibers. In fact, for the same filling up coefficient of fibers, the resistance of composite reinforced by agave fibers is quite the same as the resistance of the composite reinforced by glass fibers.

Figure 5 shows two kinds of breaking : the first one ① is in the polyester matrix reinforced by agave fibers and the second ② is in the same matrix but reinforced by glass fibers. These picture shows very well the difference between the adherence of glass and agave fibers in the polyester matrix.

CONCLUSION

From the interesting mechanical behaviour of agave fibers in polyester matrix and polyepoxyde ones, under a one direction strength, we conclude that this kind of fibers can be used to reinforce composite structures. The behaviour of agave fibers under multidirectional strengths is under study.

The obtained results show that it is possible to use composite materials reinforced by agave fibers in many applications such as car interior, machine covers...

These kinds of applications, encourage the development and the industrialisation of the agave fibers.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. HAMER, Fiberglass linked to long disease, New Scientist, October 24, 1992.
- [2] P. BLSNER, Allergic and irritive textile dermatitis, Schweiz Med Wochenschr, 1994 Jan 22. 124(3). P111-8.
- [3] Work elaborated in collaboration with the Botanic Laboratory of INAT : Institut National d'Agronomie de Tunis, represented by Professor T. HADDAR.
- [4] G.W.LOCK, Thirty years'sisal research in Tanzania, LONGMANS, GREEN AND COLTD, 1962.